

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Urinova Tursunoy Urinovna

EXPLANATION OF SEWING AND EMBROIDERY TERMS IN CLOTHING DESIGN IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/IYUN

